

Perception on Use of Educational Broadcasting as Teaching Aid among Public Secondary School Students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the level of awareness of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid among public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, as well as their perceptions on its level of use and associated challenges. The cross-sectional design study explored Communication Perception Theory, adopted a survey of 377 randomly selected respondents, who responded to a questionnaire, and analysed emanating data with simple percentages and mean scores. Findings indicate that while the students are moderately aware that educational broadcasting can be used as teaching aid, they perceive the level of use as very low and perceive poor electricity supply, inability of teachers to harness educational broadcasting into teaching, limited access to electronic gadgets in schools and lack of locally relevant contents as challenges. Findings corroborate scholarly notions that educational broadcasting is barely used as teaching aid in schools due to lack of skilled teachers and facilities. Findings also uphold the assumption of the Perception Theory by indicating that although students view educational broadcasting as a substitute for conventional classroom instruction, they do not benefit from it. The study

recommends that government and school administrators should encourage the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aids.

Keywords: *Formal education; Instruction; Radio; School subjects; Teaching and learning; Television.*

INTRODUCTION

The use of radio and television programs to teach in formal, informal and non-formal learning settings is known as educational broadcasting. It has also been described as the dissemination of educational messages through radio and television to defined audiences in a bid to enlighten them and develop their knowledge bases in specific fields (Ijeh & Ojebode 2017). According to Imhanobe (2019), educational broadcasting explores the dynamics of radio and television to promote the effectiveness of education, while Haque and Talukder (2017) aver that it as the process by which teachers and students jointly generate meanings in their brains by utilising spoken and non spoken messages packaged and presented as television and radio programmes to enhance learning. These programmes are known as educational because they are purposefully conceived, planned, produced and disseminated in ways that promote learning among consumers. Educational broadcast programmes are therefore deliberate attempts to explore the principles and philosophy of broadcasting to improve teaching and learning through formal, informal and non formal educational programmes (Ijeh & Onojeghwo 2009). Although educational broadcasting covers formal, informal and non formal domains of education, this study focused on formal educational broadcasting, described by Nkwam-Uwaoma and Onu (2017) as the use of radio and television to teach school subjects/courses with the goal of making it easier to cover the required curriculum for examinations. Ortyoyande (2016) supports this claim when he posits that instructional television and/or radio programmes enhance the effectiveness and productivity of the learning process.

The use of educational broadcasting to promote teaching and learning of school subjects is not new in Nigeria (Ismail, Othman, Amiruddin & Ariffin, 2017). Educational broadcasting began in the country in 1932 with weekly transmission of

educational radio programmes by the Radio Diffusion Service (RDS) under the defunct Post and Telegraph Department (P&T) on English language, Mathematics and History (Ijeh & Ojebode 2015; Otuya-Asohro & Ijeh 2024). Later on October 31, 1959, the then Western Region Government cited educational broadcasting as one of the cardinal objectives behind the establishment of the first television station in Africa – Western Nigeria Television (WNTV) –in Ibadan, emphasising that the premier television station would be used to educate the people living in the area (Asino & Mormah 2019; Ijeh 2014).

Educational broadcast resources in instructional delivery can serve the dual purpose of drawing students' attention and improving classroom instructions because radio and television helped compress the world into a global village and broke almost all known obstacles inhibiting mass literacy (Otuya-Asohro & Ijeh 2024; Ufuophu-Biri & Ijeh 2021). Educational broadcast programmes demonstrate progress in the field of education as they accommodate high-quality learning enhancing visuals, graphics, music, texts and motion for productive situational delivery of classroom subjects that foster students' intellectual and creative growth. These audio-visual aids in education can enhance learning, especially in terms of comprehension and retention (Ashaver & Igyuve 2013; Tang & Intai 2017). In addition, educational broadcast programmes can be recorded in audio and video formats and used repeatedly. The Covid-19 Lockdown of 2020 also exposed the relevance of educational broadcasting in Nigeria (Delta State in particular) as the state government relied extensively on it as substitute to classroom teaching and learning by deploying radio and television stations to prepare secondary school students for certificate examinations in their homes because schools were shut (Otuya-Asohro & Ijeh 2024).

Despite the ability of educational broadcasting to overcome barriers in education delivery, it appears to be poorly used in some areas because stakeholders lack the requisite knowledge of and exposure to it. Many of these resources are not accessible in many schools and where they are, teachers either lack necessary skills to deploy them effectively in teaching or are not interested in learning how to use them (Ijeh 2019). This study therefore seeks to find out what obtains in Asaba, the capital of Delta State from the perspectives of public secondary school students.

Statement of Problem

There is evidence that although educational broadcasting influences teaching and learning greatly, it is inadequately explored in secondary schools because of financial constraints, difficulty of acquiring materials, absence of facilities and the shortage of qualified staff (Taiwo 2019). Writing on teachers' perception on technology integration, Adedokun (2018) avers that when sufficient and essential technology is available for classroom teaching, instructors are better equipped to use them to enhance teaching-learning processes. In a study on the use of educational technology in teaching and learning, Zin, Muhamad, Ahmad and Sakat (2014) report that using educational technology media in teaching and learning aid teachers to convey information that students would find interesting and that people learn through their senses, which have unique learning percentages.

The above studies indicate that a great deal of research has been done on the integration of educational broadcasting, other instruction enhancement technologies and traditional classroom teaching and learning. However, not much seems to have been done to ascertain how public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, perceive the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid. How much do they know about the possibility of using educational broadcasting as teaching aid for them? What is their perception on the level of use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid in Asaba and what do they perceive as challenges to it? These questions and the absence of ready answers indicate obvious gaps in knowledge which this study on perception on use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid among public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, attempts to fill.

Objectives of the Study and Research Questions

The objectives of this study are to:

1. examine the level of awareness of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid among public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria;
2. ascertain the perceived level of use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid among public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria and

3. find out what public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, perceive as challenges to the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid.

In pursuit of the above objectives, the study sought answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the level of awareness of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid among public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria?
2. What is the perceived level of use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid among public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria?
3. What do public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, perceive as challenges to the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid?

Delimitation of the Study

The study is limited in scope to public secondary school student in Asaba, the capital of Delta State, Nigeria, in the 2024/2025 academic session. The study is also limited to the students' level of awareness of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid in Asaba, as well as their perceptions on both level of use and challenges of educational broadcasting as teaching aid in public secondary school in the area.

Literature Review

Secondary School Students' Awareness of Educational Broadcasting a Teaching Aid

Education is a significant tool for advancing instruction and learning, which contributes to the overall development of both the individual and the society. The expansion of education has put pressure on educational institutions worldwide to employ media broadcasts and technology as teaching tools in order to impart the necessary information and skills to pupils (Olumorin, Onojah & Bello 2021). Effective tactics must be used to provide high-quality education, which may not happen if students are unaware that educational broadcasts are being used as teaching tools. According to Ashaver and Igyuve (2013), students' educational development frequently uses the instructional materials that the media provide. As a result of this continuous use of the media for educational purposes, instructional media have become widely accepted among academics both inside and outside of Nigeria.

Many secondary school students recognise that educational broadcasting is a good storyteller, which encourages learning, thereby giving them opportunity to combat ignorance (Zin et al 2014). When WNTV was established in 1959, the then Western Regional Government of Nigeria acknowledged this reality of using educational broadcasting as a substitute to classroom teaching and learning, especially in rural regions where the government at the time lacked enough teaching staff to support its free education programme. Since then, teaching secondary school subjects has benefited from educational broadcasts and it has aided the growth of education in Nigeria (Taiwo 2019). Numerous studies have examined the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid in the classroom as effective means of facilitating procedural demonstration and of communicating complex concepts and ideas in an engaging and interactive way (Zheng, Warschauer, Lin & Chang 2016; De Sousa, Richter & Nel 2017). According to Shah and Khan (2015), information and animation on screens offer educational experience different from written text and enhance critical thinking. By implication, audio-visual instruction aids support students' learning processes to their admiration. Students reported feeling more involved in flipped classrooms, which are blended learning approach that combine online instruction, conversations and audio-visual resources. This is because it encourages them to read and watch visual learning materials and this multimedia educational environment offers constructivist learning environments that allow students to consciously experiment and participate in their education (Malik & Agarwal 2012). This increased student responsibility for their own learning, enhanced engagement and better attention are some of the benefits of media in teaching-learning processes that eventually boost the efficacy of the educational process (Reddi, 2013).

Use of Educational Broadcasting as a Teaching Aid in Secondary Schools

The use of broadcasting to serve educational objectives is known as educational broadcasting and according to Ijeh (2019), this process of learning and acquiring information empowers students, supports their growth and advance general education. Educational broadcasting may be used as a teaching tool to reach students with instruction in their native tongues. As a result, using instructional broadcasting

in the classroom improves student learning. Television talk shows (in particular) can be very exciting and engaging to students, which can lead to enthusiastic collaborations to complement reading and teaching. This suggests that teachers' use of educational broadcasting as teaching aids can enhance exposure to authentic materials such as TV series that can provide students with motivating and contextualised vocabulary, as well as opportunities to observe language being spoken by natives in real-life situations (Ijeh & Ojebode 2017). In order to foster student engagement and meaningful learning, educators might employ educational broadcasting to teach and acquire professional ethics. It has been demonstrated that watching TV or listening to the radio enhances listening abilities, which in turn affects speaking and writing abilities. By generating curiosity, offering real-world examples, and enhancing language proficiency, television use in the classroom can improve student learning (Asino & Mormah, 2019). Students are aware that teachers can utilise educational broadcasting as a teaching tool to increase student engagement significantly by giving them access to a range of captivating images, including practice activities, project films, animated movies, digital books, among others. Increased teacher-student contact might result from the use of educational broadcasting in the classroom. According to Ijeh and Ojebode (2015), teachers may use interactive materials like projected films, video classes and lots more to get students interested and encourage active involvement. Additionally, providing feedback in real time improves classroom interactions and makes learning more active. Therefore, educational broadcasting can facilitate more collaborative and successful learning by bridging the gap between students and teachers (Ijeh, 2019). For this reason, Asino and Mormah (2019) define educational broadcasting as instructional materials that come from a teacher in a studio at a remote place, either live or recorded. The recording is sent to a transmitter, which then transmits the message to receivers at different places via air waves. In this way, the target learners receive the instructional materials without meeting the teacher. In this scenario, television and radio are considered traditional media that teachers can use for interaction and engagement with students outside the classroom. Educational broadcasting therefore strengthens the nation's education enterprise by minimizing imbalances in access to quality education and maximizing educational opportunities

(especially in rural schools handicapped by shortage of qualified staff and equipment). It also improves the quality of learning by employing effective teaching strategies and additional audio-visual resources to help teach topics when there is a shortage of qualified school subject instructors. Educational broadcasting as teaching aids in secondary schools can enhance learners' participation by inspiring students with engaging instructional materials, audiovisual aids and more individualised attention in the comfort of their homes, thus supporting curricular implementations. Also, by providing timely and efficient delivery through the gradual introduction and use of indigenous or national languages, educational broadcasting as teaching aids can provide civic programmes at the primary and secondary levels to foster civic awareness and national unity. It can equally be deployed to disseminate pertinent information that keep educators informed about innovations and practices in the curriculum as well as how to use new media approaches to support and engage in teacher training programs for both pre-service and in-service teachers (Ijeh & Ojebode 2017; Asino & Mormah (2019).

Challenges to the Use of Educational Broadcasting as Teaching Aid

Today's secondary schools face several obstacles to the efficient use of educational broadcasting to teach with the lack of instructional tools as the most significant. According to Dhakal (2020), many instructors expressed dissatisfaction about the lack of teaching resources in schools. Findings about additional difficulties with using teaching aids in secondary school instruction revealed that students perceive that the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid may be hampered by teachers' laziness, lack of improvisational skills and strategies as well as lack of resources (textbooks, materials, time and administrative or authoritative support) (Capper 2003). It may therefore be safe to aver that instructors would perform better on the job the more they include these technologies into their teaching process. For effective implementation in a particular environment, it is essential to comprehend the elements that influence instructors' intentions to include electronic media into their lessons. The issue is that new technologies are posing challenges to electronic media in secondary schools in a number of ways, including availability, accessibility

as well as teacher specialization, qualifications and utilization. Schools need to have access to the technological media before they can be used to help students study.

Students' inability to control their broadcast-based learning activities is a problem and might cause disruptions in the classroom. According to Haque and Talukder (2017), parents could find it difficult to understand the scope and character of their kids' at-home education. Even though television has been around for a while, some teachers openly oppose it as a legitimate teaching tool (Dhakal 2020). The lack of excitement for educational broadcasting is partly caused by worries about the alleged high expense of creating high-quality instructional television shows. According to Cheung (2017), teachers' opinions on television-based learning vary, as some of them oppose its usage because of their jobs or perceived over-importance placed on the medium. While Kumar, Rose and Silva (2008) submit that instructors who have favourable opinions on educational broadcasting are more integrated than those who have unfavourable opinions, Matthew and Alidmat (2013) opine that instructors' views affect their attitudes about how to convey subject matter and their readiness to modify their teaching methods. This suggests that successful integration into classroom practices depends on knowing and addressing teachers' views towards it.

Lack of funding, policy framework, inter-ministerial cooperation, skilled personnel and poor public awareness of the importance of educational broadcasting limit its use for formal education (Ijeh 2019). In order to guarantee content quality control, funding, and sustainability, governments, education experts and broadcasters in Nigeria need to work together effectively to create pro-educational broadcasting legislation and regulate educational broadcasts. In order to decrease the public's preference for entertainment programs over educational broadcasts, innovations to make educational broadcasting appealing to viewers and advertisers should be introduced, along with adequate provisions for training and retraining educational broadcasters to increase their competency (Otuya-Asorho Ijeh 2024; Taiwo 2019).

Theoretical Framework (Communication Perception Theory)

The Communication Perception Theory (CPT) postulates that people are selective in how they perceive communication messages and that this selectivity affects the way

they decode messages received, which sometimes may be different from the intended meaning encoded by the sender (Folarin 1998). By clarifying the complex process by which individuals or groups choose, arrange, and interpret sensory stimuli to create a cohesive worldview, CPT as introduced by Berelson and Steiner's in 1964, indicate that factors such as social interactions, psychological inclination, experience and cultural possibilities significantly influence the way we perceive and respond to every communication activity (Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma 2017; Folarin 1998). It involves selective attention, which focuses on information that supports views or behaviours, and selective exposure, where people pay attention to media messages that support predetermined attitudes. Furthermore, recalling information depending on perceived relevance is known as selective retention. The theory hypothesizes that individuals actively seek out interesting information while rejecting less pertinent ones (Adedokun 2018). This hypothesis is relevant to our study because it clarifies how students view educational broadcasting as a complement or outright substitute for conventional classroom instruction. Students' knowledge of and access to instructional broadcast media programmes in their learning are subsequently influenced by this. It is critical to ascertain if students reject the value of educational broadcasting or see it as a formal teaching tool. The difficulties presented by educational broadcasting in the educational system are highlighted by Ashaver and Igyuve (2013), who raise the possibility of opposition to its implementation.

Methodology

The study adopted a cross-sectional research design with survey research method. The study population comprised 21,981 being the total number of students in public secondary schools in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, within the period of the study (Source: Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Asaba, 2025). The study determined the sample size of 377 from the Krejcie and Morgan Table for sample size determination and adopted a multi-stage sampling technique to select participants who responded to a questionnaire. The multi-stage sampling included simple random sampling by balloting to select 5 out of the 9 public secondary schools in Asaba and disproportionate quota sampling to select 75 students from 3

and 76 from 2 of them. The third stage of sampling involved the use of cluster sampling to select 12 or 13 students from each of the 6 classes (JSS 1-3 and SSS 1-3) of the 5 secondary schools via simple random sampling using n^{th} occurrence based on equal intervals determined from the class rosters. The study deployed questionnaire as instrument for data collection and adopted simple percentages and mean scores for data analysis.

Data Analysis

The study recorded 76.39% questionnaire return rate as 288 out of the 377 copies distributed were retrieved and found usable. The remaining 89 copies of the questionnaire, representing 23.61% contained defective responses and therefore not suitable for data analysis. Emanating data show that female student-participants were slightly higher than their male counterparts with a frequency of 147 representing 51.04% as against 141 (48.96%), majority of them (71 [24.65%]) fell within the 14-15 years age bracket, followed by those in the 12-13 years bracket (64 [22.22%]); 16-17 years (54 [18.75%]); respondents less than 12 years (50 [17.36%]) and lastly those above 17 years (49 [17.02%]). The distribution of respondents according to their classes was almost equal because of the use of cluster sampling viz: SSS 3 (50 [17.36%]); SSS2 and SSS1 (49 [17.1%]) each; JSS2 (48 [16.67%]); JSS3 (47 [16.32%]) and lastly by respondents in JSS 1 (45 [15.63%]). See Table 1.

Table 1: Questionnaire Return Rate and Demographic Composition of Respondents

Category	SN	Description	F	%
Questionnaire Return Rate	1	Suitable for data analysis	288	76.39
	2	Not suitable for data analysis	89	23.61
Total			377	100
Sex of Respondents	3	Female	147	51.04
	4	Male	141	48.96
Total			288	100
Age of Respondents	5	Less than 12 years	50	17.36
	6	12-13 years	64	22.22
	7	14-15 years	71	24.65

	8	16-17 years	54	18.75
	9	Above 17 years old	49	17.02
Total			288	100
Class of Respondents	10	JSS 1	45	15.63
	11	JSS 2	48	16.67
	12	JSS 3	47	16.32
	13	SSS 1	49	17.01
	14	SSS 2	49	17.01
	15	SSS 3	50	17.36
Total			288	100

Research Question 1 sought to find out the level of public secondary school students' awareness of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. Emanating data (Table 2) indicates that an overwhelming majority of respondents (257 [89.2%]) are only moderately aware of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aid in Asaba, Delta State. Those who reported high level of awareness (16 [5.6%]) are almost equal to those who are not aware at all (15 [5.2%]).

Table 2: Level of Awareness of the Use of Educational Broadcasting as Teaching Aid among Students of Public Secondary Schools in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria.

SN	Level of Awareness	F	%
1	Very aware	16	5.6%
2	Moderately aware	257	89.2%
3	Not aware at all	15	5.2%
Total		288	100

Arising from the above data analysis, the study concludes that the level of public secondary school students' awareness of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aids in Asaba, Delta State, is moderate.

Research Question 2 examined public secondary school students' perception on the level of use of educational broadcasting as a teaching aid in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. Emanating data (Table 3) indicate that majority of the respondents (199 [69.1%]) reported zero availability of educational broadcasting as teaching aids for

secondary school subjects in Asaba during the period under review. This is followed by 51 respondents, representing 17.7%, who reported weekly availability. 21 of them (7.3%) said the educational programmes were available as teaching aids for secondary subjects few times in a week while the minority (17 [5.9%]) reported seeing educational broadcasts that qualified as teaching aids in secondary school subjects daily

Table 3: Perceived Level of Use of Educational Broadcasting as a Teaching Aid among Public Secondary School Students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria.

S/N	Perceived Frequency of Availability	F	%
1	Daily	17	5.9
2	A few times a week	21	7.3
3	Once a week	51	17.7
4	Never	199	69.1
Total		288	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Arising from the analysis above, this study concludes that public secondary school students' perceive the level of use of educational broadcasting as a teaching aid in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, as very low.

Research Question Three inquired into what the public secondary school students perceive as challenges to the use of educational broadcasting as a teaching aid in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. Respondents were requested to mention what they perceived as the three most prominent challenges to the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aids in public secondary schools education in Asaba, the capital of Delta State, Nigeria. Accordingly, this data point yielded a total of 864 responses. The data distribution as shown on Table 4 indicates that majority of the responses (271 [31.4%]) indicated poor power supply as the most prominent challenge to the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aids in Asaba. This is followed by inadequate teacher training on how effectively use educational broadcasting programmes as teaching aids (213 [24.6%]) and limited access to relevant electronic gadgets (204 [23.6%]). Minority of the responses indicated lack of relevant and locally focused contents with a frequency of 176, representing 20.4%.

Table 4: Perceived Challenges to the Use of Educational Broadcasting as Teaching Aids among Public Secondary School Subjects in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria.

S/N	Perceived Challenges	f	%
1	Limited access to electronic devices or internet connection	204	23.6
2	Lack of relevant and locally focused content	176	20.4
3	Inadequate teacher training on effectively using educational broadcasting programs	213	24.6
4	Poor power supply	271	31.4
Total		864	100

The data distribution compels this study to conclude that the perceived challenges to the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aids among public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, in the order of prominence are poor electric power supply; inadequate teacher training on effective use of educational broadcasting programmes as teaching aids; limited access to relevant electronic gadgets and lack of relevant and locally focused contents.

Discussion of Findings

Findings in this study indicates that the level of public secondary school students' awareness of the use of educational broadcasting as teaching aids in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, is moderate. This finding corroborates the submission of previous studies that in line with the CPT's paradigm of selectivity, people's awareness of media contents depends on perceived relevance such that they actively seek out what they consider as interesting information and reject what they consider as less pertinent ones (Adedokun 2018; Ashaver & Igyuve 2013). On the contrary, the finding negates the submission that secondary school students recognize and admire educational broadcasting as a teaching aid that allows students to consciously experiment and participate in their education (Malik & Agarwal 2012).

Another finding in this study indicates that public secondary school students perceive the level of use of educational broadcasting as a teaching aid in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, as very low. This finding is at variance with the submissions of scholars in the field that educational broadcasting is widely used as teaching aids in secondary

schools to inspire students, enhance learners' participation and provide timely and efficient delivery of educational contents, while keeping educators informed about innovations in curriculum and new approaches that support their teaching (Asino & Mormah 2019; Ijeh & Ojebode 2017). Conversely, this finding supports the view that socio-economic constraints exist to keep the level of use of educational broadcasting for formal education in Nigeria low, in spite of its potentials (Capper 2003; Ijeh 2019).

The third finding in this study indicates that educational broadcasting is not significantly used as teaching aids in public secondary schools in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, because of poor electric power supply; inadequate teacher training on effective use of educational broadcasting programmes as teaching aids; limited access to relevant electronic gadgets and lack of relevant locally focused contents. This finding places poor power supply and inadequate teacher training on effective use of educational broadcasting programmes as teaching aids ahead of limited access to relevant electronic gadgets, thus partly corroborating the submission of Dhakal (2020) who avers that lack of televised instructional tools (same as 'limited access to relevant electronic gadgets') is the most significant of them.

Conclusion

The study concludes that while public secondary school students in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, are moderately aware that educational broadcasting can be used as teaching aid for them, they perceive the level of actual use as very low. The study also concludes that the perceived challenges to the use of educational broadcasting in secondary school education in Asaba among the students, in the order of prominence are poor power supply inadequate teacher training on effective use of programmes as teaching aids; limited access to relevant electronic gadgets and lack of relevant locally focused contents.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion above, the study recommends as follows:

- Government, education managers and school proprietors should ensure regular electricity supply to schools in Asaba in particular and in Nigeria in general.
- Government, educationists and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should make deliberate effort to acquaint teachers with skills necessary for effective incorporation of educational broadcasting as a teaching aid.
- Government, educational managers, curriculum developers and broadcasters should work together to initiate, plan and produce educational radio and television programmes with locally relevant contents for use as teaching aids in schools in Asaba and beyond.

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